

Begging among Physically Healthy Adults in Addis Ababa: Reasons, Strategies and Mental Wellbeing

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Abstract:- Beggary is not welcomed in our society and in many religious teachings. However, many people, including those who are physically healthy, are earning a living from begging. The purpose of this study was to assess the reasons forcing physically healthy adult beggars to lead life through begging, strategies they employed and mental wellbeing. Data were collected from 100 participants selected through purposive and convenience sampling techniques by the help of interview, FGD and Mental Health Continuum Scale. The findings revealed that invitation, poverty, and unemployment were among the reasons accounting for begging. The results of the quantitative data revealed that the mean score of mental wellbeing of physically healthy beggars (56.6) was found above average (35); indicating that the participants were mentally healthy too. The analysis of the t-test shows that there was significant difference between addicted and non-addicted adult beggars in mental wellbeing; $t(df = 36) = 6.8, p < .01$. The researcher recommends that to minimize or ultimately stop the behavior, reasons accounting for begging need to be emphasized and improved.

Keywords:- Begging, physical health, mental wellbeing.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Developing countries, specially, those in Africa are characterized by inadequate health conditions, limited education opportunities, internal conflict, poverty, and the likes (Sireen, 2017). Ethiopia, as one of developing countries, is vulnerable to the above and other similar problems such as high unemployment rates and displacement due to war. Abebaw (2003) argues that Ethiopia is a host of tremendous problems some of which are famine, poverty, political instability, unemployment, underemployment, ethnic conflict, war, displacement, migration, and so forth. According to Güneralp et al, (2017), Sireen (2017), and Van Dijk&Fransen (2008) urbanization is the other critical problem in developing countries. Exposure to these and similar other problems has created the expansion of various social problems like begging in Ethiopian cities especially in Addis Ababa (Abduselam and Belay, 2021; Jelili, 2006).

Based on the type of people engaged in begging behavior and on the purpose of beggars, the term begging has been defined in various ways. In a document aimed at assessing the socially uprooted sectors of the society developed by Ministry of Labor and Social Affairs of Ethiopia, begging was defined as "...A method of earning ones living from the income obtained by other sectors of the society using age, health, and economic conditions" (MOLSA, 1992, p. 2). Furthermore, the following definitions were included in the document:

- Begging is an activity emanated from poverty and destitution where by the person tries to feed him/herself.
- It is a behavior practiced to obtain from others what one is unable to get by oneself.
- Begging is a request directed to the rest of the society to bring oneself out of misery and poverty.
- Begging is an act of asking alms that is essential for survival, for solving temporary problems, or for fulfilling some cultural and religious commitments.

Furthermore, Groce and his colleagues defined begging as "an activity which allows an individual to call upon people with whom he or she has no close ties for small donations to meet his/her basic needs. It is a mechanism through which the community ensures that its very poor members will not starve" (Groce et al., 2014, p. 9).

Although when begging actually began globally is unknown, it was well documented that it is a worldwide phenomenon (Ahamdi, 2010; Groce et al., 2013; Jelili, 2006; MoLSA, 1992; Woubishet, 2005). There are many evidences from research works showing that begging behavior is more obvious in developing countries (Abebaw, 2003; Ebenezer et al., 2018; woubishet, 2005). These research works similarly indicated that the problem of begging was high in many African countries. In Ethiopia, as one of the Africa's developing country, the practice of leading life through begging and earning a living from the behavior is rampant (Antehunegn and Abduselam, 2019, Abduselam and Belay, 2021).

The practice of begging in Ethiopia is thought to begin with religious practices and disintegration of the traditional culture of support (Negese, 2008). The traditional and original cultures of most Ethiopian ethnic groups were characterized by support, sympathy and compassion for each other and for the economically poor. During ancient period basic needs for the needy were met primarily by relatives, cultural and religious organizations, and clan groups (personal discussion with friends, September, 2016).

The disintegration of traditional culture paves the way for the disappearance of informal support systems. The disintegration of the traditional support systems or the absence of informal support system along with the flourishing of individualistic culture gave birth to the occurrence of begging in Ethiopian cities (MoLSA, 1992; Negese, 2008).

Addis Ababa is a fast growing city where almost all the Ethiopian ethnic groups are represented (PEFA, 2008). The capital city covers 527 square kilometers from Ethiopian total area. The population density is close to 5,165 individuals per square kilometer available. The Central Statistics Agency of Ethiopia estimated the current Addis Ababa's population to be more than 4.5 million people (CSA, 2020). Since the city is relatively equipped with better facilities, infrastructure, and industries when compared to other cities, it remains a main destination for migrants migrating to the city from both rural and urban areas. Internal migration in turn has been among the factors that led the city to overcrowded living conditions, social fragmentation, crime, violence and ultimately poverty (MoFED, 2006; Netsanet, 2009).

The problem of poverty in Addis Ababa is exacerbating and a significant proportion of its dwellers are believed to live in scary living conditions. Netsanet (2009) stated that poverty is high in the central part of the city than in the peripheries. Poverty was found to be among the major reasons pushing individuals to beg in streets of Addis Ababa (Groce et al., 2014; Teweldebrhan, 2011; Woubishet, 2005). It is one of the factors leading individuals to resort to begging including physically healthy beggars.

Concerning the reasons that led people to resort to begging, several factors are repeatedly reported by various researchers in Ethiopia. Poverty (Fireyihun, 2011; Teweldebrhan, 2011; Woubishet, 2005), family breakdown (Fireyihun, 2011), societal disintegration and illiteracy, (Teweldebrhan, 2011), rural-urban migration and displacement due to drought, famine and war (Tatek, 2009), religious obligation (Kerebih, et al., 2007), peer pressure and illness (Lucas, 2007), political reasons, unemployment and underemployment (MOLSA, 1992), and urbanization (Woubishet, 2005) were among the major reasons. Of course, these studies focused on individuals who had, at least, physical reasons to beg (disabled beggars, old-age beggars, child beggars, and so forth). The researcher of the current study speculated that these reasons may not work for the physically healthy beggars. Therefore, it was attempted to investigate if there was any different factor that pushed the participants of this study to earn a living from begging.

It is not uncommon to observe physically healthy adult people earning a living from begging in streets of Addis Ababa (Abduselam and Belay, 2021; Groce, et al., 2014; Negese, 2008; Samuel, 2017). Begging among physically healthy adults is becoming a major way of earning a living. Although socially prohibited, there are various written documents, videos, and television programs revealing that Addis Ababa is becoming a city where healthy adult individuals are making money and leading their life through

begging (Negese, 2008; Tatek, 2009). In Ethiopia, as in many other countries, beggary as a livelihood strategy is not encouraged. It is more unethical especially for those who are physically healthy and be able to take on other formal economic activities. In addition beggary is not encouraged by various religions. Nevertheless, the field is attracting significant number of physically healthy individuals (Abduselam and Belay, 2021, Antehunegn and Abduselam, 2019). Why physically healthy individuals beg while it is both socially and religiously prohibited? Are they mentally healthy?

Mental Health or Mental Wellbeing (MW) is not merely seen as the absence of mental illness. The World Health Organization (WHO) defined MW as “a state of well-being in which the individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a contribution to his or her community” (WHO, 2004, p 12). MW is believed to consist of three components: emotional well-being, psychological well-being, and social well-being. Emotional wellbeing, the first component of MW, is defined as one’s satisfaction and happiness in life. Psychological well-being indicates optimal personal functioning which includes six aspects: 1. self-acceptance: which refers to a positive attitude toward oneself, 2. personal growth as the feeling of sustained development and possibilities, 3. purpose in life: referring to having a purpose and orientation in one’s life, 4. environmental mastery: representing a feeling of being able to handle a complex environment, 5. positive relatedness: having satisfying and intimate relationships (including abilities as empathy, affection and intimacy) and being interested in the well-being of others, and 6. autonomy: comprising being self-determined and independent (Ryff, 1989). Keyes (1998) defined social wellbeing as people’s valuation of their circumstances and functioning in society. It refers to how much individuals see themselves thriving in their social life. Social wellbeing is characterized by five dimensions: 1. social acceptance: refers to a positive view on other people and the ability to accept others as who they are, 2. social contribution: which refers to the belief of being able to fulfill and achieve activities and goals which are valuable for the society, 3. social integration: representing a good relation to the community and society, 4. social actualization: implying the belief that society has the potential for positive changes, and 5. social coherence referring to a logical and apprehensible view of the social world with interest in the social environment and social interaction (Keyes, 1998).

Nowadays, there are many research works conducted on emotional wellbeing, psychological wellbeing, and social wellbeing. There are also sufficient evidences showing that mental wellbeing (which includes the three components mentioned above) has been investigated thoroughly (Keyes, 2007; Taneva, 2016). It has also been shown well that mental wellbeing is positively associated with physical health. But, as far as the researcher’s knowledge is concerned, there is no independent research work conducted so far, in Ethiopia, on the MW of physically healthy adult beggars. Therefore, it was found essential to assess the MW of physically healthy adults who are earning a living from

begging. In general, the objectives of this study were to assess the reasons pushing physically healthy adults to beg in streets, the strategies they employed to gain the attention of alms givers, and to test their mental wellbeing.

II. METHODS

A. Research Setting

Addis Ababa is located in the foothills of *Entoto* Mountains and stands 7,726 feet above sea level. Unlike many other African capitals the foundation, growth, and development of Addis Ababa are not rooted in colonization (Bahru, 2001). It is a city where almost all the Ethiopian ethnic groups are represented (PEFA, 2008). The capital city holds 527 square kilometers in Ethiopian area. The population density is estimated to be near 5,165 individuals per square kilometer available. According to CSA (2020), the current Addis Ababa's population is estimated to be more than 4.5 million with a lower rate of infant mortality than the national average.

Addis Ababa has emerged as a city that has both national and international significance. It serves as a seat of various international organizations and embassies. The city is often called the African Capital due to its historical, diplomatic and political significance for the continent (Gebre, 2008).

Addis Ababa is being largely populated mainly by people who are migrating from rural areas due to drought, political crisis, regional wars, government compulsion, debilitation of natural resources, search for employment opportunities, and lack of social services (Abduselam and Belay, 2021; Woubshet, 2005). The majority of the migrants usually find themselves in difficult socio-economic circumstances in the capital. Many migrants are forced to engage in various forms of jobs to earn a living and to tackle the challenges put up on them. They are also forced not to choose among jobs because of the high unemployment rate existing in the country (CSA, 2020).

Mesalemiya	Piassa	Torhailoch
Awutobustera	RasMekonnin Bridge	Biherawi
Merkato	Arat Kilo	Sengatera
GojamBerenda	Megenagna	Tikuranbessa
Teklehaimanot	Filwuha	Kazanchis
Abinet	Legehar	Kality
Mexico square	Urael church	

After the identification of the specific areas where the target population was largely found, participants were selected from four sub-cities and specific areas in the sub-cities as given in table 1.

III. SAMPLE SIZE AND SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

A. Qualitative Data:

Twenty three physically healthy beggars of whom 10 were females and the remaining 13 were males were selected through purposive and convenience sampling techniques from selected areas of Addis Ketema, Arada, Lideta and Kirkos sub-cities for the interview. Purposive sampling technique was used because beggars who were

Four sub-cities, namely; Addis Ketema, Arada, Lideta, and Kirkos were selected due to the reasons indicated below; and that the behavior under question was commonly practiced in some selected areas of these sub-cities (the sub-cities are given in figure 1).

- The areas are found in sub-cities which are located at the center of the city (see figure 1).
- The sub-cities are relatively high business areas.
- These areas are highly populated /constitute more than 40 % of the capital's population (Netsanet, 2009)/.
- The majority of the city's poor are found in these sub-cities (Netsanet, 2009).
- Street dwellers can easily get access to locations where they can pass night times such as bridges, worshipping areas and market places.
- There are well-known churches and mosques. Relatively large number of people usually performs day-to-day religious obligations in religious institutions found in these sub-cities.

B. Population and Participants:

The population of the study was physically healthy adult individuals (18 to 40-years-old) who were earning a living from begging in Addis Ababa. This population was considered as productive age group who were the backbone of the country. This group of people was the one that was responsible for country's achievement in economic sector.

According to an interview held with the officials from LSAB of Addis Ababa city government, the exact number of physically healthy adult people who were earning a living from begging in Addis Ababa was unknown. But the bureau has identified areas (sub-cities) where physically healthy adult beggars were largely found and practice the behavior. Although beggars were spread in all sub-cities, the target population of this study was frequently observed in selected areas of some sub-cities. The following areas were well known by housing the target population.

physically healthy were the target of the research and hence being physically normal was the purpose. Likewise convenience sampling was used because it allows getting readily and easily available participants. Beggars were available and easily reached while they were begging. Concerning samples for the Focus Group Discussion (FGD), 10 participants were selected on purposive sampling and availability sampling techniques where six of them were males and the remaining four were female beggars. Availability sampling was used because it was found so difficult to bring beggars together which were selected through other methods. This was due to the fact that participants were moving from an area to the other area; and from a street to another street due to the nature of their job. Beggars who were found near each other in time and place

were asked to take part in the FGDs if they were found physically healthy.

Therefore a total of 33 beggars (19 male and 14 female) were participated in the qualitative study. Likewise, three officials (a female and two males) from Labor and Social Affairs Bureau (LSAB) of Addis Ababa City Government were also included in the study through purposive sampling technique. The purpose of including officials from LSAB of Addis Ababa city government was that the bureau is among the organizations closely working on vulnerable groups and those who are living in streets.

B. Quantitative Data:

Initially, while writing the proposal of this study, it was aimed at merely measuring the mental wellbeing of physically healthy beggars. For this purpose, 36 beggars were selected and data were begun to be collected. While observing the data it was learnt that there were differences between beggars who were using drug (addicted) and who were not (non-addicted). The difference in the responses between drug users and others forced the researcher to form two groups—addicted and non-addicted. It was then decided to collect data from both groups separately and compare their mean. It was found important to add more participants to both addicted and non-addicted groups for the purpose of fulfilling the assumptions of a test used to compare means of participants. Among the previous 36 participants, 22 were found addicted and the rest 14 were non-addicted. Thus, 33 physically healthy adult beggars who were totally dependent on substances, and 31 beggars who were not frequently using substances (non-addicted) were selected.

Two informal organizations (Nisirochu, and Yared and his brother) who were regularly feeding beggars, street dwellers, and other poor people were contacted. There were 280 individuals who were being fed by Yared and his brother, and more than 800 by Nisirochu. Among individuals who were being fed by Yared and his brother, 38 non-addicted beggars were identified by the help of the feeders of the organization and given number cards from 1-38. Nineteen beggars who hold odd numbers were identified and selected for the study. The same procedures were employed to select samples from individuals being fed by Nisirochu. Twenty four non-addicted beggars were identified, again, by the help of the feeders of the organization and given number cards ranging from one to twenty four. Accordingly, 12 beggars who were given odd numbers were selected for the study. Therefore, a total of 31 non-addicted beggars have been selected based on the procedure mentioned above.

Participants for the addicted group were selected from Nisirochu. Sixty-six physically healthy adult beggars who were using substances regularly were identified and asked to make a line. The second, the fourth, the sixth, etc in a queue were separated from others. Thus, 33 participants who were found in even numbers in the queue have been selected. In general, a total of 64 beggars (27 females and 37 males) were selected to fill out the scale meant for the purpose of measuring mental wellbeing.

C. Tools of Data Collection:

Two varieties of tools were used. The first variety was the one used for the purpose of screening and identifying participants. The researcher developed two types of tools for the purpose of identifying physically healthy beggars from other beggars (e.g., child beggars, old-age beggars, disabled beggars, etc), under the first variety. These were observation and screening tool. The second variety was those meant for collecting primary data from participants. These were an interview guide, FGD guide, and scale.

D. Observation:

The observation checklist was meant for the purpose of inspecting beggars as physically healthy or physically unhealthy. Since the participants of the study were the so called physically healthy adult beggars, it was through this observation checklist that the participants were initially assessed. The checklist consists of items assessing physical conditions such as the condition of hands, legs and locomotion. Initially, beggars were observed by relying on the observation checklist. If the beggar met the criteria sought in the primary observation checklist, then the action followed was administering the screening tool. This checklist consists of four items (e.g., “Are the hands of the beggar normal?”, “What about his/her legs?”, “Does the person walk properly?”etc).

E. Screening Tool:

Like that of observation checklist, the purpose of screening tool was to differentiate physically healthy adult beggars from unhealthy ones. Since the participants of this study were beggars who were physically fit enough during data gathering period and who can engage in other legitimate forms of businesses requiring physical health and strength, the researcher developed items that were helpful to identify physically healthy beggars from unhealthy ones. The tool was developed by relying on medical research works and through consultation of professionals from medicine. The items of the screening tool focused mainly on major diseases inhibiting individuals to engage in various forms of businesses requiring physical fitness and their perception of the conditions of their physical strength.

The screening tool was constructed from 11 items. The tool focused on major diseases like diabetes, hypertension, heart disease and the likes (e.g., “I have never diagnosed with heart disease.”, “There is no wound and/or injury on my body that inhibits me from participating in formal economic activities.”). It was also focused on the condition of eyes, legs and hands (e.g., “I can see and recognize a friend at a distance others can see.”, “I can hear a sound at a volume others find acceptable.”). Furthermore, the screening tool assessed whether participants felt that they were physically healthy enough so that they were able to take part in any other jobs requiring certain amount of physical strength (e.g., “Do you feel that you are physically healthy and fit enough to engage in jobs requiring physical strength?”, “Any other illness inhibiting you from jobs requiring physical fitness?”).

Each item has two response alternatives: 'YES' or 'NO'. It was after the beggar has answered 'YES' for all the items that he/she was considered as a participant of the study. If one of the items was answered 'NO' then the beggar was considered as physically unhealthy and rejected from the study.

F. Interview Guide:

The interview guide was administered after the beggar was identified as a participant by the help of observation checklist and screening tool. The guide had two parts. The first part assessed demographic variables such as age, sex, place of birth and level of education (e.g., "Your Sex", "Age in Years", "Level of Education / 1. Unable to read and write, 2.Elementary, 3.High School, 4. Certificate and above"). The second part explored reasons accounting for begging (e.g., "Select the reason/s forced you to begin begging in street"). This part also sought answer for the strategies employed by participants to get the attention of alms givers so that they would easily be able to collect money or other things they needed (e.g., "What kind of strategy/strategies you employ to easily solicit money from people you beg").

G. Focus Group Discussion:

The FGD guide consists of two questions requiring participants' responses on reasons accounting for begging and strategies employed by them (e.g., "Tell me the reason/s forced you to lead life through begging", "What kind of strategy/strategies you employ to easily get the sympathy of people you beg?").

The first FGD was conducted at Piassa, Jegole Square. The discussion was conducted among four female participants. The second FGD of the same guide was carried out around Filwuha which consisted of six male beggar participants. The items of the FGD were developed in English language by the researcher and translated into Amharic by himself and a language expert in Addis Ababa University. Each FGD lasted for about 18 to 22 minutes. Though the FGDs were carried out with consent, the main challenge faced during discussion was that participants were unhappy with the time spent on discussion since the discussions were held during their working (begging) hours. It was found impossible to conduct FGD at times other than their working/begging hours.

H. Scale:

Mental wellbeing was measured by the Mental Health Continuum Short Form /MHC-SF/ scale. The scale was derived from the long form Mental Health Continuum /MHC-LF/, which consisted of seven items measuring emotional wellbeing, six 3-item scales (or 18 items total) that measured Ryff's model of psychological wellbeing, and five 3-item scales (or 15 items total) that measured Keyes' model of social wellbeing. While the MHC-LF consisted of 40 items, the MHC-SF consists of 14 items that were chosen as the most prototypical items representing the construct definition for each component of wellbeing. Three items were chosen to represent emotional wellbeing (e.g., "I am interested in life", "I am satisfied with life"), six items were chosen to represent psychological wellbeing (e.g., "I have something important to contribute to society", "I belong to a

community"), and five items were chosen to represent social wellbeing (e.g., "I am good at managing the responsibilities of my daily life", "I have warm and trusting relationship with others").

The MHC-SF scale is validated for use with individuals aged 12 years or older and has been used by many researchers (Keyes, 2007; Keyes, Dhingra, & Simoes, 2010; Keyes, Eisenberg, Perry, Dube, Kroenke, & Dhingra, 2012; Keyes, & Simoes, 2012). The scale has shown excellent internal consistency (> 0.80) and discriminant validity in adolescents and adults in various countries (Keyes, 2005 b; 2006; Keyes et al., 2008; Westerhof, & Keyes, 2010). The original MHC-SF scale measures the frequency with which respondents experience each symptom of positive mental health, and thereby provide a clear standard for the assessment and a categorization of levels of positive mental health that is similar to the standard used to assess and diagnose major depressive episode in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders. But for this research purpose, the scale response category was modified into 5 point scale ranging from 'strongly agree' to 'strongly disagree' (the reliability of the modified scale is given in table 2).

The mean of the scale ranges from 14 (1×14) – 70 (5×14). Based on this range, a mean of 35 is an average score. Mean scores below 35 indicate low mental wellbeing whereas scores above 35 are within normal range. Seventy is the highest score possible.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS

Qualitative data were analyzed thematically. In using thematic analysis a deductive approach was employed. The researcher began the analysis by having some themes at hand, before beginning to go through the data, which were expected to occur in the data. Then familiarity with data was obtained through a thorough overview of all the data collected.

Phrases, sentences, and expressions having relevance with the themes were highlighted with various colors to create codes. Codes were created in a way that each code describes the ideas expressed by the participants. Some of the codes developed were: Undeserving Beggars, Strong Beggars, Beggars that Seem Healthy, Street Dwellers, Being Uncertain, 24 hours, incidence, profitable business, well-known job, 'Qifela', 'Yegile', 'Derash', 'teqetari' etc. After looking at the codes thoroughly, patterns leading the researcher to the themes were identified. Irrelevant codes were discarded and some unusual Amharic terms used by the participants were changed to commonly understandable terms (for instance the term 'Qifela' was changed to begging; 'Teqetari' to full time beggar). Based on the codes, each theme was defined and named (e.g. 'Undeserving Beggar' is named as 'Physically Healthy Beggar'). Finally, the themes developed were Physically Healthy Beggars, Commonness, Incidence, Full Time Beggar, Attractive Daily Income, Profitable Job, yegile (many years of experience).

Some of the interviewees were audio-recorded with permission. The recorded materials were transcribed precisely and put under each theme.

Both descriptive and inferential statistics were employed for the analysis of quantitative data. Percentage was used to assess the demographic characteristics of participants. Mean was computed to test the mental wellbeing of participants. Finally, independent samples t-test was used to see the statistical differences between addicted and non-addicted beggars in mental wellbeing.

V. ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Although ethical principles are important in all kinds of studies, the degree of importance is high for studies conducted on group of people like beggars. Therefore, fundamental ethical principles were strictly followed.

The data collection instruments including the tape recorder were accompanied by informed consent form and participants were informed that participation in the research is voluntary. Moreover, the respondents were identified by a self-generated letters and numbers for confidentiality.

While presenting the informed consent form, participants reported that they were deceived frequently by many previous researchers. Any attempt of deception was tried to be controlled and eliminated, as much as possible, in this study.

VI. FINDINGS

A. Characteristics of Respondents

There were 33 physically healthy beggars who took part in the qualitative part of the study, of whom 14 were females and the remaining 19 were males. Among them, 23 beggars (10 female and 13 male) have been participated in the interview while the remaining 10 beggars (four female and six male) have been participated in the FGD. Furthermore, a female and two male officials from LSAB of Addis Ababa City Government were interviewed. Therefore, a total of 36 participants (15 female and 21 male) were participated in the qualitative part of the study. The quantitative data involved 64 (27 females and 37 males) physically healthy beggars. Therefore, a total of 97 beggars (41 female and 56 male) and three officials (a female and two males) have been involved in the study (Look at table 3).

Among the 97 physically healthy beggars who took part in this research, 29 (29.9 %) were born in Addis Ababa whereas 68 (70.1 %) were born outside the capital. Therefore, it is clear that the majority of the respondents were born outside Addis Ababa and moved to the capital for different reasons. Unfortunately, among the 68 respondents born outside Addis Ababa, eight of them were migrated to the capital for the purpose of making money from begging. They came to the capital aiming that they would be able to lead their life through begging and that they can earn a living from begging. When we look at the other's main reasons of leaving their home land, data revealed that 19 of them reported that they came to Addis Ababa for search of

job; 18 reported poverty as a reason; 12 reported problems associated with family; three mentioned displacement due to politics; and the rest eight were called up to Addis Ababa by friends and/or relatives previously migrated to the capital city.

Additional characteristics of participants are depicted in table 4, and in subsequent paragraph.

Two very remarkable results from the above table were that: 1) there was participants who were earning a living from begging after having completed their education from higher education institutions; 2) although they were leading their life through begging, more than 40 % of the participants who took part in the study reported that they had children whom they were taking care of during data collection period.

B. Reasons Accounting for Begging

In this section, it was attempted to identify why physically healthy adults beg while they were able to engage in culturally appropriate businesses. Before presenting the reasons that led physically healthy adults to lead their life through begging, it has to be clear that reasons that led deserving beggars (disabled beggars, child beggars, old-age beggars, etc) were thoroughly investigated by researchers. It was speculated, in this research, that there could be different reasons that probably pushed physically healthy individuals to beg since the participants of this study had no outwardly observed reason forcing them to beg. To this end, new and unique reasons that led physically healthy adults to earn a living through begging were identified (represented by asterisk in the table below). Nevertheless, the reasons accounting for deserving beggars to beg, as revealed by previous researchers have also been found accountable for physically healthy beggars too.

Table 5 illustrates the factors that pushed participants who participated both in qualitative and quantitative data to resort to begging. It has to be noted that participants were given the chance of selecting more than one factor that they believed was/were among the major reason/s forced them to begin life in streets.

According to the officials working at LSAB of Addis Ababa city government, some of the reasons that pushed physically healthy individuals to lead their life through begging were religious beliefs, work habit of the community, profitability of the field, and the culture of our society associated with responding to the questions of beggars.

"Many of the healthy beggars observed in streets are not actually poor. They are not the right person to beg. They beg because they know that begging is currently a profitable job. As I heard the healthy beggars are fighting with disabled beggars in streets. Disabled beggars are complaining to our office that the healthy ones are not allowing them to beg in areas where they are available. The reason is clear that if both able bodied and disabled beggars beg together, obviously people prefer to give to disabled ones" (LSAB, 14).

The other official explained about the reasons that forced physically healthy individuals to beg as follows:

It is agreed that we, Ethiopians, are lazy people. We want to be rich as fast as possible. I think religion played its own role on us to develop poor work habit. We collected beggars and other street dwellers from streets and gave them training on various professions. After completing the training, we provided them 12,000.00 birr believing that they can begin their own business. Some of them were found while begging in streets. Mindless, it is after taking the training and the money that they were found in streets. This is simply because they don't want to exert maximum effort to get money from other jobs. You know, begging is so simple that everybody can do it (LSAB, 15).

C. Strategies Used by Physically Healthy Adult Beggars

In the context of this study, begging by physically healthy beggars was defined as asking people with whom the physically healthy beggars have no close ties for a non-reciprocated gift such as money, food, and cloth. The result obtained from participants of the study, in relation to strategies or techniques used to approach almsgivers, was found almost similar with techniques that have been used by disabled beggars, old-age beggars, child beggars, and other types of beggars in previous research findings. The only unique strategy obtained from the data was that participants go certain distance with the person whom they beg. The FGDs of the current study revealed that participants used various begging strategies to get the attention of almsgivers so that they can easily attain their goal.

In most cases I show respect for people I beg by using words of respect such as 'YeneGeta', 'Yemesafintzer', 'YelijHabtam', etc (A discussant number 2, Filwuha).

The other participant said:

Although I have to frequently change techniques, many times I appear as if I ate nothing for hours. Sometimes I go certain distance with the person I beg so that I will get room to get sympathy of the person (Discussant number 1, Piassa).

A 28-years-old female participant of the FGD narrated that she was using some religious terms, wearing used up clothes and occasionally new clothes, using words that show that she was in a very serious hunger, telling that she has children to take care.

In general, the strategies physically healthy beggars used included:

- Representing themselves as sick
- Wearing worn out clothes and occasionally new clothes
- Using religious words and pretending to be a religious leader
- Using words that show respect
- Looking starved
- Expressing that they have many responsibilities such as caring and feeding children, educating children, taking care of older parents, etc.

- Going certain distance with the person whom they beg

D. Mental Wellbeing

As discussed above, MW comprises of three components: emotional, psychological, and social. In this section the mean of each component of the participants and the overall mean was presented and analyzed. This was done to indicate that whether the MW of those who were physically healthy but earned a living from begging was high or low. Finally, data concerning the mean difference between the addicted and non-addicted groups were presented and analyzed.

Since emotional wellbeing was measured by 3 items of 5 point Likert scale, the expected average score was 7.5 and the highest score was 15. Accordingly, emotional wellbeing of participants was 11.9, which implies that their emotional wellbeing was above the average. Psychological wellbeing was the second component of MW measured by 6 items of 5 point Likert scale. The findings indicated that the mean score of the participants (24.2) was significantly higher than the average score (15) and very close to the highest possible score (30). Similarly, data revealed that the other component of MW, i.e., social wellbeing, was found to be significantly higher (20.5) than the average score (12.5), where the maximum score was 25. In general, it was found that all the three components of MW of participants was high (56.6) and hence it can be said that beggars who were physically healthy were mentally healthy too.

In relation to the mean difference between the two groups, same procedures were employed. Initially, emotional wellbeing of the two groups was compared using independent samples t-test then followed by the comparison of the remaining components. Table 6 shows the output of the independent samples t-test of the three components of MW.

As can be seen from the table, the level of significance corresponding Levene statistic F is very small (.000) in all the three components. This implies that the assumption of homogeneity of variance was violated and hence the 'Equal variances not assumed' t-test statistic was used. Accordingly, the result of the analysis of emotional wellbeing indicated that there was significant difference between addicted and non-addicted beggars, $t(df = 39) = 5.13$, $p < .01$. The mean values also indicated that emotional wellbeing of addicted beggars ($M = 10.3$) was lower than the non-addicted ones ($M = 13.6$). The data also revealed that the psychological wellbeing of addicted group showed significant difference from the non-addicted group, $t(df = 38) = 5.89$, where $p < .01$. This significant difference was also revealed by the mean values because the mean value of non-addicted beggars (27.3) was significantly higher than that of addicted beggars (21.2).

Similarly, the result of the analysis between the two groups in relation to social wellbeing revealed significant difference. The social wellbeing of those who were not using substance was better than those who were using various substances, $t(df = 40) = 4.57$, $p < .01$. The mean values also indicated that social wellbeing of addicted

beggars ($M = 18.7$) was significantly lower than the non-addicted ones ($M = 22.5$).

The final output of the t-test was the test conducted for the three components of mental wellbeing. As shown in table 7, the result of the analysis of MW between the two groups showed significant difference, $t(df = 36) = 6.8$, $p < .01$. The mean values also indicated that mental wellbeing of addicted beggars ($M = 50.3$) was significantly lower than the non-addicted ones ($M = 63.4$).

VII. DISCUSSION

A. Reasons Accounting for Begging:

People who are physically fit enough to earn a living from socially legitimate ways are resorting to earning a living from begging in Addis Ababa. This is due mainly to the fact that the traditional ways of helping the needy are disintegrated, as already indicated in the background section. Poverty, family problems, lack of job or unemployment, profitability of begging when compared to other jobs were among the common reasons made participants of the study lead life through begging.

In general, many of the reasons accounting for begging, as identified in this study, were those already showed by previous researchers. Furthermore, unique reasons that seem working for physically healthy adult beggars were identified. According to the finding many participants got into streets to beg because they were called up on by other beggars. The other unique reason identified in the current study was the fact that begging does not require special knowledge and skill when compared to other forms of jobs. Others jobs demand sufficient knowledge and skill, specially acquired from going through educational institutions at higher levels.

B. Strategies Physically Healthy Adult Beggars Used:

Prior to data collection for this research, the researcher had a belief that physically healthy beggars would probably approach almsgivers through techniques which were not used by old-age beggars, disabled beggars, and other individuals who have some sort of reasons to beg. Unfortunately, the result obtained from participants of the current study showed that physically healthy beggars were found using similar strategies used by the previously mentioned beggars to approach almsgivers. Data showed that participants of the study were found using no different strategies except that they were going few distance together with the person whom they begged. This technique was found helpful for participants because moving certain distance with almsgivers gave them extra room and time to explain their need and to get their mercy.

C. Mental Wellbeing:

Mental wellbeing was conceptualized, in this research, as a construct having three components: emotional wellbeing, psychological wellbeing, and social wellbeing. Initially the mean score of each component was analyzed and followed by the overall mean scores. This was followed by the comparison of the mean differences between the addicted and non-addicted groups. Accordingly, the mean scores of each component of MW were found above average. Thus

physically healthy adult beggars who took part in the study were found mentally healthy too. Based on this finding, adults who were found begging in streets were those who can create chances of earning a living from socially accepted and legitimate ways because they were both physically and mentally healthy.

The findings concerning the mean differences in MW among the addicted and non-addicted groups indicated significant differences. The mean scores of addicted beggars in all the three components of MW were found significantly lower than that of the non-addicted beggars. Those who were not totally using substances or those who were using substances occasionally were found to be mentally healthier than those who were regularly abusing various types of substances. The use of substances could be one of the reasons contributing to low mental wellbeing. It has been widely documented that substances are chemical compounds that affect the mind and body (Galvani & Livingston, 2012). Substance abuse was among the factors lowering mental wellbeing. Many research findings revealed that substances alter a person's brain structure and function resulting in long-term psychological effects such as depression, anxiety, and increased aggression (eg., AAC, 2021).

According to AAC (2021), lack of social support was one of the reasons accounting for using drugs. The data obtained from many of the participants of the current study showed that they were disconnected from their family and the community and that they had poor social support. The only support they were receiving was from beggars with whom they beg.

There are research evidences showing that MW is positively associated with physical health (Taneva, 2016). The findings of this research also showed that physically healthy beggars who took part in this study have been found mentally healthy too, although there was speculation that people who beg in streets being physically healthy could have some form of mental illness.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Many reasons accounting for beggary among physically healthy adults have been identified in this research. Poverty was the main reason followed by inability to get employed and problems associated with family of participants. The other very interesting reason was invitation towards begging. Significant number of physically healthy beggars was found begging in streets through invitation by a beggar friend, relative, or neighbor. The other reason accounting for the commonness of begging by healthy individuals was its profitability. The findings of this study revealed that participants were receiving better income than many employees hired at government organizations after having completed their first and second degrees. Similarly, religious beliefs, work habit of the community and the culture of our society associated with responding to the questions of beggars have been noted as reasons for being a beggar among physically healthy adults.

MW was comprised of three components—emotional, psychological, and social wellbeing. Two research questions were framed. The first research question assessed whether the physically healthy participants were mentally healthy too? In this regard, the mean scores showed that physically healthy adult beggars who took part in this study were found mentally healthy too, in all the three components. They were found emotionally, psychologically, and socially healthy. The second research question raised about MW was whether the MW of addicted beggars (who regularly used various substances) and non-addicted beggars (those who did not use or who were using substances only sometimes) was statistically different. Accordingly, the differences in MW between the two groups were found statistically significant. The mean scores of those who were using substances regularly (addicted beggars) were found significantly lower than the non-addicted group.

IX. RECOMMENDATIONS

The researcher of the current study wanted to fearlessly underline the fact that no country can achieve its full potentials in a situation that large number of a country's young and adult population resorted to making living from begging in streets. The researcher argues that although the practice of begging does potentiate opportunities of getting money for unemployed physically healthy adults, the risk countries face and the overall negative impact deserve more government attention. On the basis of the findings, the researcher proposed the following recommendations.

- Beyond all, working on reasons leading to begging and trying to improve them need to be given due attention.
- Participants of the study had no physical health related reasons forcing them to lead their life through begging. They were also found mentally healthy. Therefore, those who give alms need to differentiate the needy (disabled beggars, old-age beggars, child beggars, etc) from the able bodied beggars.
- Concerned organizations have to develop intervention strategies that enhance employment opportunities. Simultaneously, any plan concerning intervention methods need to consider the structural causes of poverty.
- Begging has to be prohibited for various reasons. Preserving public order and inducing people to work rather than to beg are among the major reasons. It has to be seriously taken into consideration that the country is missing productive age groups due to begging.

DECLARATIONS

- **Ethics Approval and consent to participate:** The data collection instruments including the tape recorder were accompanied by informed consent form. Participants were informed that participation in the research is voluntary.

The questionnaire and methodology for this study was approved by professors in the school of psychology of Addis Ababa University on June 2019. But there is no trend of giving written letter for such approvals.

- **Availability of Data and Materials:** Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analyzed during the current study.
- **Competing Interests:** The author of this article declares that there is no competing interest.
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- **Authors' Contributions:** Not applicable in this research.

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The author of this article is a beginner researcher and a lecturer at Woldia University (Ethiopia). Woldia University is one of the institutions destroyed as a result of war conducted between Ethiopian government and Tigray Peoples' Liberation Front (TPLF). Currently, the author is a PhD candidate in Addis Ababa University and expected to complete his PhD in two months period.

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TABLES

Table 1: Sub-Cities and Specific Areas from which Samples Were Selected

Addis Ketema Sub-City	Arada Sub-City	Lideta Sub-City	Kirkos Sub-City
AwutobusTera	Piassa	Teklehaimanot	Filwuha
GojamBerenda	RasMekonnin Bridge	TikurAnbessa Megenagna	Biherawi Mexico Legehar

Table 2: Summary of the Reliability of the Scale

Variable	Number of Items	Cronbach’s Alpha
Emotional Wellbeing	3	.77
Psychological Wellbeing	6	.73
Social Wellbeing	5	.75
Total	14	.775

Table 3: Summary of the Participants Involved in the Study

	Beggars			Non-Beggars	
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female
Interview	13	10	23	2	1
FGD	6	4	10	–	–
Scale	37	27	64	–	–
			97		3

Table 4: Characteristics of Beggar Respondents

Age in Years	Level of Education		Number of Children					
	Freq.	Per.	Freq.	Per.				
< 20	37	38.1	Don’t read and Write	6	6.2	No children	53	54.6
20-30	41	42.3	Elementary	61	62.9	One child	29	29.9
31-40	19	19.6	High school	28	28.9	Two children	13	13.4
			Certificate and above	2	2.0	Three children and above	2	2.0
Total	97			97			97	

Table 5: Reasons Accounting for Begging

Factors	Qualitative		Quantitative		Qual + Quan		Total
	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	
* Recommended by others	6	2	7	4	13	6	19
Unable to find job	5	11	12	18	17	29	46
Poverty	10	14	18	21	28	35	63
Family problems	5	11	8	12	13	23	36
Political reason (war, displacement, etc)	2		1	5	3	5	8
profitable job	3	4	7	4	10	8	18
* Other jobs are physically too demanding	4	2	3	3	7	5	12
I have no one who take charge of me	3		16	2	19	2	21

Table 6: Independent Samples T-Test Output of each Components of Mental Wellbeing

		Independent Samples Test								
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variance			t-test for Equality of Means					
		F	Sig	t	df	Sig (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Diff.	95% CI	
								L	U	
EW	Equal variances assumed	35.6	.000	5.01	62	.000	3.27957	.65	1.9	4.5
	Equal variances not assumed			5.13	39	.000	3.27957	.63	1.9	4.5
PW	Equal variances assumed	22.7	.000	5.7	62	.000	6.04790	1.05	3.9	8.1
	Equal variances not assumed			5.9	38	.000	6.04790	1.03	3.9	8.1
S W	Equal variances assumed	20.5	.000	4.5	62	.000	3.75660	.84	2.1	5.4
	Equal variances not assumed			4.6	40	.000	3.75660	.82	2.1	5.4

Table 7: Independent Samples T-Test Output

		Independent Samples Test								
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variance			t-test for Equality of Means					
		F	Sig	t	df	Sig (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% CI	
								L	U	
Equal variances assumed		50.417	.000	6.589	62	.000	13.08407	1.98	9.1	17.1
	Equal variances not assumed			6.776	36	.000	13.08407	1.93	9.2	16.9

FIGURES

Fig. 1: Sub-Cities from Which Samples were Selected